

Formulation, Development and evaluation of Nitrofurantoin tablets drug delivery systems

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Abstract

Nitrofurantoin is a synthetic nitrofuran derivative widely used for the treatment and prevention of urinary tract infections (UTIs). It exhibits both bacteriostatic and bactericidal properties depending on its concentration. The formulation of Nitrofurantoin tablets aims to achieve optimum bioavailability, stability, and patient compliance. This review summarizes various approaches to the formulation and evaluation of Nitrofurantoin tablets, focusing on excipient selection, manufacturing methods, quality control parameters, and recent advances in sustained or controlled release systems.

Keywords: Nitrofurantoin; Hydroxyl Propyl Methyl Cellulose (HPMC K4M; HPMC K100M); Xanthan Gum; Sustained Release

1. Introduction

The oral route is considered to be the most convenient for administration of drugs to patients. Oral administration of conventional dosage forms normally dissolves in the stomach fluid or intestinal fluid and absorption from these regions of gastro-intestinal tract (GIT) depends upon the physicochemical properties of the drug. It is a serious drawback in conditions where localized delivery of the drugs in the urinary tract is required or in conditions where a drug needs to be protected from the hostile environment of upper GIT. Dosage forms that deliver drugs into the urinary tract or colon rather than upper GIT prefers number of advantages. A traditional oral sustained release formulation releases most of the drug, after the dosage form pass from the stomach. Hence, the drug should have absorption window either in the duodenum or intestine or urinary tract [1]. The main goal of sustained drug delivery systems is to improve the effectiveness of drug therapies [2]. Sustained release drug system is "any drug or dosage form modification that prolongs the therapeutic activity of the drug". Ideally a sustained release oral dosage form is designed to release rapidly some pre-determined fraction of the total dose in to GI tract. This fraction (loading dose) is an amount of drug, which will produce the desired pharmacological response as promptly as possible and the remaining fraction of the total dose (maintenance dose) is then release at a constant rate. Nitrofurantoin is a urinary tract antibiotic [3]. The short biological half-life (0.3 to 1 hour) and dosing frequency more than one per day make Nitrofurantoin an ideal candidate for sustained release [4]. To reduce the frequency of administration from four times daily to two times daily, to minimize the side effects of nausea and emesis and to improve patient compliance.

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2. Material and methods

Material: Nitrofurantoin was obtained from QMED Pvt. ltd Bhaktapur, Nepal and the excipients present in the SR granules are: hydroxypropyl methylcellulose-K4M, HPMC K100M, Xanthan gum, Anhydrous Lactose, Magnesium stearate, Talc were obtained from Amtech Med. Pvt. Ltd. Kathari-4, Morang as a gift. All the chemicals used were of analytical grade and purchased from an authorized dealer.

Drug-Drug and Drug-Excipient Compatibility Drug- Drug and Drug-Excipient Compatibility was assured by FT-IR spectroscopy. Preparation of sustained release matrix tablet of nitrofurantoin tablets were prepared by direct compression method. Specified quantity of nitrofurantoin, polymers such as HPMC K4M, HPMC K100M, xanthan gum, other excipients like lactose, magnesium stearate and talc weighed accordingly to the formula given in table no.1. All the materials except magnesium stearate and talc were transferred in a mortar and pestle and mixed thoroughly. This powder was passed through sieve no #80. To this add weighed quantity of magnesium stearate and talc. Each batch formulation powder blend was weighed to accurate single total tablet weight (710mg). Tablet was compressed with Single head rotary tablet compression machine.

Table 1 Material and Supplied By

Nitrofurantoin	QMED PVT ITD Bhaktapur, Nepal
HPMC K4M	Yarrow chem PVT ITD, Mumbai
HPMC K100M	Yarrow chem PVT ITD, Mumbai
Xanthan gum	Yarrow chem PVT ITD, Mumbai
Anhydrous Lactose	Mehta chemicals, Bangalore
Magnesium stearate	Signet Chemical Corporation Mumbai
Talc	Karnataka Fine Chem, Bangalore

Table 2 Equipment Used

Sr. No	Equipment
1	Fourier Transform Infrared Spectrophotometer (IR. Thermoscientific Nicolet is 10)
2	UV/VIS Spectrophotometer (up Jasco 2016) No: Qc.cp-057
3	pH Meter H12216 pH/ ORP/ISE Meter
4	Ultra-sonic
5	Electronic Balance Sartorius No: Oc-Cp.059
6	Hardness Tester Rimek- India. No: cp.010.
7	Disintegration Tester (disintegration tester -bj-3)
8	HPIC 2020
9	Dissolution Tester (Rc-80C) No: Qc-cp-071
10	Tablet Machine

	Rotary tablets press machine Zp-7
11	Friability Tester (Cjy-300D Tablets friability tester)
12	Thickness Tester Vernier (Stainless hardened)
13	Oven Incubator) Accelerate Stability Study Champer

2.1. Formulation And Evaluation of Nitrofurantoin

Table 3 Formulation Table

Ingredient in mg	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
Nitrofurantoin	200	200	200	200	200
Xanthine gum	300	_	_	_	150
HPMC K4M	_	300	_	150	150
HPMC K100M	_	_	300	150	_
Anhydrous lactose	200	200	200	200	200
Magnesium starts	7	7	7	7	7
Talc	3	3	3	3	3
Total weight	710	710	710	710	710

2.2. Evaluation of Nitrofurantoin

- Evaluation of pre-compression flow properties of powderblend
- Organoleptic properties -Organoleptic properties of API like color, odor and stability were observed a recorded. Solubility was observed in methanol and sodium hydroxide.
- Bulk Density -Bulk density was measured using bulk density apparatus. Fixed weight of powder was poured in the measuring cylinder and volume was recorded.
- Bulk density = Bulk weight/Bulk volume Tapped Density -Fixed weight of powder was poured in the measuring cylinder and tapped 50 cycles multiple times. Volume was recorded after each 50 tapping cycles until fixed (concurrent) reading was obtained. The tapped density was obtained by using following equation: Tapped Density = Bulk weight/Tapped volume.
- **Weight variation-** The weight variation test would be satisfactory method of determining the drug content uniformity. Twenty tablets randomly were taken from each batch and weighted individually, calculating the average weight, and comparing the individual tablet weights to the average. The average weight of one tablet was calculated.
- **Diameter test** -The diameter test one of tests which used for determination of the tablets size, it is done by taking five tablets from each batch randomly. Diameter may obtain by using suitable micrometer.
- **Thickness test** -The thickness test of five tablets was picked from each batch randomly and thickness was measured individually using "Vernier- caliper" (Electronic Digital Caliper). It is expressed in millimeter and average was calculated.
- **Hardness test** -The hardness test or tablet crushing strength. The force required to break a tablet in a diametric compression was measured using digital tablet hardness tester. It is expressed in kg/cm. Five tablets were randomly selected from each batch and hardness of tablets was determined by using digital hardness tester. The mean values and standard deviation for each batch were calculated.
- **Friability test** -The friability test is performed to assess the effect of friction and shocks, which may often cause tablet to chip, cap or break. Roche fryolator was used for the purpose. Pre-weighed sample of five tablets from each batch were placed in the fryolator, which was then operated for 100 revolutions. After 100 revolutions the tablets were dusted and reweighed. Compressed tablets should not lose more than 1% of their weighed.

- **In-vitro disintegration time-** The in-vitro disintegration time was determined using disintegration test apparatus. A tablet was placed in each of the six tubes of the apparatus and one disc was added to each tube. The time in seconds taken for complete disintegration of the tablet with no palatable mass remaining in the apparatus was measured in seconds.

3. Result and discussion

Table 4 Evaluation parameters of Nitrofurantoin

Formulation Code	Hardness	Thickness	Friability%	Average Weight	Drug Content
F1	7.5 ± 0	5.5	0.74	710.3	98.29 ± 0.05
F2	6.66	5.5	0.47	710.17	99.54 ± 0.64
F3	6.5 ± 0	5.4	0.72	710.42	99.05 ± 0.4
F4	6±0	5.48	0.70	709.36	100.35 ± 0.16
F5	7.33 ± 0.288	5.01	0.50	709.4	101.76 ± 0.52
F6	6.5 ± 0	5.02	0.83	710.5	100.63 ± 0.09

4. Conclusion

Matrix tablet of nitrofurantoin was successfully prepared by direct compression method, using different types of matrixes forming polymers like HPMC K4M, HPMC K100M, Xanthan gum. Matrix tablets are easy to prepare. They are cost effective and exhibit predictable release behavior. So, the ultimate aim of the present study was to prepare twice daily sustained release matrix tablets of Nitrofurantoin for improved patient compliance, better therapeutic efficacy, less side effects and reduced dosage regimen with less toxicity for treatment of urinary tract infection. In conventional dosage form it undergoes First pass metabolism, that is way it shows poor bioavailability of 45-56%. So, due to this disadvantage to improve bioavailability sustained release matrix tablet was formulated. Following conclusions have been drawn from the present study. Ø Compatibility of drug and polymer was confirmed by FTIR studies.

Ø the formulation blend was subjected for pre-compressional evaluations such as angle of repose, bulk and tapped density, compressibility index and Hausner's ratio and was found to be in the specified limit.

Ø the evaluation data for properties such as hardness, thickness, friability, weight variation, drug content indicated that the prepared matrix tablet was within the specified standards.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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